

FORMATION OF COMMUNICATION CULTURE BASED ON DIALOGUES IN AN ENGLISH LESSON IN A HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

Almira Shamsunovna Nigmatullina

Senior Teacher, Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Fergana, Uzbekistan

E-mail: almira.nigmatullina@ferpi.uz

Guzal Djaxonobodxanovna Xodjayeva

Senior Teacher, Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Fergana, Uzbekistan

E-mail: guzalhodzaeva26@gmail.com

Annotation: This paper examines various non-traditional forms teaching a foreign language, which contribute to increasing internal motivation. In our opinion, non-traditional forms of foreign language teaching languages have a number of advantages according to certain criteria in comparison with traditional.

Keywords: interethnic communication, tertiary education institutions, self-education, permanent group, training curriculum, lack of motivation

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются различные нетрадиционные формы обучения иностранному языку, способствующие повышению внутренней мотивации. На наш взгляд, нетрадиционные формы обучения иностранным языкам имеют ряд преимуществ по определенным критериям по сравнению с традиционными.

Ключевые слова: межнациональное общение, вузы, самообразование, постоянная группа, учебная программа, отсутствие мотивации.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada chet tilini o'rgatishning turli noan'anaviy shakllari ko'rib chiqiladi, bu esa ichki motivatsiyani oshirishga yordam beradi. Bizning fikrimizcha, chet tillarini o'qitishning noan'anaviy shakllari an'anaviy tillarga nisbatan ma'lum mezonlarga ko'ra bir qator afzalliklarga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: millatlararo muloqot, oliy o'quv yurtlari, o'z-o'zini tarbiyalash, doimiy guruh, o'quv dasturi, motivatsiya etishmasligi

In the current globalization period, where interpersonal communication—including interethnic communication—is becoming increasingly important, knowing a foreign language is no longer considered a luxury but rather a necessity

for society to successfully progress. Furthermore, learning a foreign language is important for raising educational standards and shaping an individual's character (because it allows one to have direct access to the cultural history of another nation). It is not unexpected that interest in foreign language education has significantly increased recently in our nation; an increasing number of courses are opening with the primary goals of raising students' English language proficiency and fostering communicative competence. Graduates from secondary and tertiary education institutions are required to meet a minimum proficiency level in a foreign language. Why is this not taking place? There are many possible causes for this situation, but in the context of contemporary standards, we believe that the primary factor is a lack of motivation, which can be strengthened through non-traditional forms of training, when the student's potential for self-education is highlighted (when the teacher serves as a "conductor," showing the student the direction and path that they must master on their own with the teacher's assistance).

The lesson is the primary organizing structure used in modern schools for instruction. A lesson is a way to arrange instruction for a permanent group of students of the same age; classes follow a set timetable and follow the same training curriculum. It is well known that a lesson has the following characteristics that set it apart from other types of education: - it is a finished, time-limited portion of the educational process in which specific educational tasks are solved; - each lesson is scheduled and has a set amount of time allotted for it as well as educational content. Unlike other forms of educational organization, it is a permanent form that guarantees students' systematic acquisition of knowledge, skills, and abilities; - all students must attend classes in order to study a system of knowledge that is divided into lessons according to a certain logic; - it is a flexible form of educational organization that allows you to organize frontal, group, and individual educational activities for students; - cooperative activities between the teacher and students provide opportunities for teamwork among the children; helps students' mental development and the development of their cognitive traits (activity, independence, curiosity). Depending on the qualities used as a foundation, didactics offers a variety of lesson formats. They categorize instruction into many categories based on how it is delivered, such as lectures, talks, debates, independent work of UCHN new, etc. In accordance with the phases of educational activity, which include: introductory lessons, lessons for first familiarization with the subject matter, lessons for concept

formation, lessons for deriving laws and regulations, lessons for applying knowledge in real-world situations, lessons for material repetition and generalization, control lessons, and combined lessons.

A foreign language course has several characteristics. A foreign language lesson is unique in that it is a link in a series of lessons rather than a stand-alone educational unit. The dynamics of the educational process are fulfilled in this cycle of lessons: the objective of the previous lesson serves as the basis for the next, establishing the intimate relationships between the lessons and guaranteeing progress toward the ultimate learning objectives. Let's look at the methodological substance of a foreign language lesson nine, or the fundamental rules that establish its characteristics, organization, reasoning, and working methods. Individualization, speech orientation, situationality, functionality, and novelty are hence the cornerstones of a foreign language education. Individual characteristics of students include motivation, interest, learning style, general development, degree of confidence in their abilities, ability and self-discipline, cultural characteristics, level of training, potential abilities and learning, language ability, intellectual abilities, learning experience, student's attitude toward the subject, psychological mechanisms of speech activity, and performance. These elements form the foundation of individualization. A few options for assignments might help you make sure the lesson is tailored to each student. It is important to design exercises so that students can work on subjects that interest them. The combination and application of different forms of individualization—individual, pair, group, and collective forms of work—helps to lessen the gap between the so-called strong, average, and weak students, according to author A.A. Kostenko in the magazine article "Individualization of the process of teaching English to primary schoolchildren". As a result, individualization aids in both kid motivation and level-diversity communication among pupils. Now let's shift the focus of a foreign language instruction to speech. A valuable lesson is imparted through language, according to E.I. Solovova, however this lesson is not about language. The lesson's practical orientation is speech orientation. It is well established that studying the principles of reading and vocabulary acquisition alone will not help one learn to read or talk. Neither will understanding the rules of grammar. Practical speech activities should take up practically the whole lesson time, according to the teacher. Ten distinct practical problems that advance the student toward his objective should be solved at each

lesson. The speech (communicative) value of phrases is also a prerequisite for a foreign language lesson's speech orientation. Phrases that are never used in everyday conversation should not be included in foreign language instruction.

The setting, the time, the personalities and roles of the parties involved in the communication, as well as the speech task they wish to accomplish during the conversation, all influence every given scenario. The association of phrases with the relationships in which the interlocutors find themselves is known as situationalism. One prerequisite for learning to speak is a situation. The circumstances encourage speech. In actuality, the environment is not the things around the interlocutors; rather, it is a system of relationships between them. The interlocutors' relationship is what drives them to make specific speech acts, such as arguing or proving, making requests or grieving. Additionally, since there is a lot of context behind speech, communication is made easier the larger and deeper these links are. The essence of situationality demonstrates that its application is inconceivable without personal individualization, as it is only through a thorough understanding of potential interlocutors—their background, interests, feelings, and status within the class team—that situations can be created in the classroom as a system of relationships. Thus, the following guidelines are determined by situationality as a part of a lesson's methodological content: Every sentence said in class should be situational, meaning it should connect to the relationships between the interlocutors; only then can a communication situation be produced in a lesson based on the relationships between the interlocutors (students and teacher); Situationality is a prerequisite for both the process of skill development, such as lexical and grammatical preparatory exercises, and the development of speaking skills.

One of the key elements in a foreign language lesson's methodological content that ensures student attention is novelty. In this context, novelty refers to the freshness of educational materials' content, the freshness of instructional formats (such as press conferences and excursions), and the freshness of task kinds; in other words, the continuous (within acceptable bounds) novelty of every aspect of the educational process.

It is expected that interactive and dynamic approaches will be employed since they are more successful and efficient.

• The case approach. There is a description of a circumstance (actual or as near to reality as feasible). Students are required to investigate the problem, put up potential solutions, and select the best one.

•The project technique entails the capacity to independently analyze a given scenario and identify a workable solution. The project method integrates creative approaches, educational strategies, research, and search.

•The problem technique is putting forward a dilemma (problem scenario, troublesome issue) and looking for answers by examining related situations (problems, phenomena). •Reading and writing as a means of fostering critical thinking is a technique designed to foster critical (independent, imaginative, and rational) thinking. The stages of challenge, comprehension, and reflection comprise the unique lesson structure provided by the technique. •Heuristic method: this approach mixes a range of gaming strategies through research, business and role-playing games, and tournaments.

• The problem-based learning approach and the research process share certain similarities. The problem is only formulated by the instructor in this instance. It is the students' responsibility to plan their research to analyze the issue.

•A modular teaching approach divides training material into didactic units, or modules. The topic, learning objectives, student profile differential, and their selection all influence how big a module gets. Numerous factors determine the strategy of choice:

• Learning objectives; • student readiness level; • student age; • study time allotted; • school supplies; • instructor preparation, both theoretical and practical.

Every teaching approach has a unique set of strategies that make it easier to put the approach into practice.

It is common knowledge that a teacher's primary responsibility is to inspire their students to learn. In the meantime, there is a wide range of research being done on motivation, and there are various interpretations of this phenomenon. The complexity of the motivational problem dictates the range of perspectives that can be used to comprehend its essence and select the best research methodologies. First, we observe that human conduct has two functionally related sides: incentive and regulatory.

Drive 16 is in charge of activating and directing behavior, while regulation controls how it unfolds in a given scenario from start to finish. The main function of

mental processes, states, and phenomena like thinking, focus, memory, perception, imagination, feelings, emotions, temperament, character, and abilities is to regulate behavior. Regarding its stimulation, or motivation, it is connected to the ideas of motivation and motive. Distinguishing these two ideas is crucial. Compared to "motive," the term "motivation" conveys a more expansive idea.

The term "motivation" has two meanings in contemporary psychology: first, it refers to a system of elements (motives, needs, goals, intentions, and much more) that determine behavior; second, it describes a feature of a process that both stimulates and sustains behavioral activity at a particular level. When attempting to explain conduct, the idea of motivation comes up. The queries "why?", "for what?", "for what purpose?", "why?", and "what is the point...?" are being sought after in this search. The answer to the question of why particular behaviors are taken is found in the causes of long-lasting behavioral changes. Regarding the concept of motivation, the definition provided to this phenomenon by one of the foremost researchers on the subject seems to us the most comprehensive: motive is the reason behind an action; external objects, ideas, feelings, and experiences can all serve as motives. Everything that encapsulated the need, to put it simply. Careful examination is needed of the methodological and psychological facets of the topic of motivation enhancement. From the perspective of learning psychology, the following elements are crucial:

- 1) Skillful encouragement from the instructor
- 2) Including the emotional domain in the educational process;
- 3) Customizing instruction for each learner; Using audiovisual materials;
- 5) Managing knowledge, skills, and abilities;
- 6) Including students in independent work throughout class; and
- 7) Fostering a collaborative and friendly environment in the classroom.

Methodologists recommend the following unconventional approaches to teaching foreign languages in order to carry out these requirements:

- 8) Presenting challenging assignments and circumstances;
- 9) Integrating the project methodology into instructional procedures;
- 10) Utilizing role-playing and educational games;
- 11) Utilizing resources for area studies;
- 12) Establishing an extracurricular activity system;
- 13) Adding language activities outside of the classroom.

The state standard states that the development of communicative competence is intrinsically linked to knowledge of sociocultural and regional studies, which also serves to boost students' interest for studying a foreign language. In order to improve the subject-content plan, the linguistic and regional component is required to correct information on regional studies in language units. Among the factors boosting its action are its regular use and careful selection. Texts on regional studies ought to contain material that is somewhat novel and significant to students. In this context, texts that provide details on the place where the language being studied is being learned, its government, children's and youth groups, etiquette quirks, and speech patterns inside its borders are all relevant. The goal of all of this is to make students realize how important it is to familiarize themselves with regional studies resources on their own. Since linguistic and regional studies cover both language instruction and the acquisition of knowledge about the nation whose language is being studied, they aid in boosting motivation. Another crucial aspect of learning a foreign language is its societal component. Culture has a significant impact on how someone develops their personality. Thus, culture in its broadest sense encompasses both more and less information about the nation, as well as background knowledge about native speakers' nonverbal cues during conversations. As such, a foundation is required from which students can learn about the nation's customs and the accomplishments of their own culture within the context of global culture. Studying a foreign language is made much more motivating by the sociocultural component, which in a way permits conversation between civilizations.

To sum up, it is important to remember that the learning environment should mimic authentic communication situations as closely as possible, as this is how the consolidation of learnt language phenomena occurs. For pupils to understand the purpose of completing assignments in the language they are studying, they must be aware of the subject and the behaviors associated with it.

Research Science and
Innovation House

Literature:

1. Djakhonobodkhonovna K. G. Problems encountered in teaching English as a foreign language //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 5 (50). – С. 165-167.
2. Ходжаева Г. Д. Использование коммуникативного подхода в обучении грамматике английского языка //Проблемы современной науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 12-2 (145). – С. 153-155.
3. Rakhmanov D. M., Khodjaeva G. D., Mamaruziev S. Ancient greek architecture //American Journal of Technology and Applied Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 18. – С. 71-75.
4. Khodjaeva G. D. Actual problems of teaching a foreign language in secondary schools //Экономика и социум. – 2022. – №. 12-1 (103). – С. 145-148.
5. Ходжаева Г. Д. Формирование Навыков Осознания Гражданских Прав И Обязанностей У Молодежи В Современном Обществе //Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 189-192.
6. Shamsunovna, N. A. (2022). The Concept, Essence, Features of the Methods and Techniques Used in Teaching Foreign Languages. European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements, 3(1), 116-118.
7. Нигматуллина, А. Ш. (2016). Проблема повышения и развития эффективности качества чтения на иностранном языке. Ученый XXI века, 95.
8. Nigmatullina, A. (2023, May). Formation and origin of ecoterminological system. In International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics (pp. 313-315).
9. Shamsunovna, N. A. (2023). Best practice of study the terminology of ecology on the basis of uzbek and english languages. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12, 69-70.
10. Nigmatullina, A. S. (2023). Main issues of reflecting ecoterms in translation. Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики, 5(5).
11. Nigmatullina, A. S. (2023). Similarities and differences in the semantic structure of environmental terms. Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики, 5(5).

12. Shamsunovna, N. A. (2022). Linguistic study of ecological terms. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 24, 652-654.
13. Nazirovich, A. U. (2022). Turizmga oid atamalarning lingvokulturologik xususiyatlari. *Conferencea*, 256-258.
14. Abdukodirov, U. N. (2020). Using of dictionary sources for improving integrated teaching methods. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(11), 230-234.
15. Abdukodirov, U. (2020). Materials development in teaching. In *мировая наука 2020. Проблемы и перспективы* (pp. 3-5).
16. Nazirovich, A. U. (2023). Methodical approaches in english teaching. *Journal of Science-Innovative Research in Uzbekistan*, 1(9), 1169-1173.

Research Science and
Innovation House

